

Better Economics for the Earth: The semiconducting principle

Amazon Book Review Series of “*Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories*”

Edward Gerald Woodward

January 4, 2025

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This is a fascinating essay on climate control and the economic aspects influencing how we react to climate control. Our 400-year history of growth and development has not been equalized by our defining problems and developing programs to overcome and obovate problems. A wonder read.

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★★★★★ **The semiconducting principle of economics**

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Screenshot. Review of “*Better Economics for the Earth*” by Woodward [1]. Reviewed in the United States on January 4, 2025.

(*) Note: This paper reprints Woodward’s review [1] appearing on the Amazon page of the title [2].

References

[1] Woodward, E. G. (2025, Jan. 4). The semiconducting principle of economics. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/RZI0T2JUSG7ES/>

[2] Vuong, Q. H. & Nguyen, M. H. (2024). *Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0D98L5K44>